

TURNING CONTROL OF A MOBILE ROBOT FOR GREENHOUSE SPRAYING

Guoqin Gao*, Qiuyue Qin, Sheng Chen

School of Electrical & Information Engineering, Jiangsu University, Zhen Jiang 212013, China

E-mail: gqgao@ujs.edu.cn

Abstract

The road of a greenhouse is both damp and narrow, and there are both ground obstacles and space obstacles in a greenhouse, which easily cause the instability problem for a four-wheel independent driving greenhouse spraying mobile robot turning in the greenhouse. In order to improve the steering performance of the greenhouse spraying mobile robot, based on the characteristics that each wheel torque of the robot can be separately controlled, the dynamic model of the four-wheel independent steering system is firstly established by using the D'Alembert's Principle and choosing the sideslip angle and the yaw velocity as the state variables. Then, based on the theory of sliding mode control, a dynamic sliding mode control strategy with exponential approaching rate is proposed by adopting the sideslip angle and the yaw velocity as the joint control variables in order to make the sideslip angle be in the stable range and make the yaw velocity track the desired value well. Finally, the simulation of the steering performance is performed using Matlab/Simulink. The control response curves of the yaw velocity and the sideslip angle of the robot's mass-center in a step input and in a sinusoidal input are obtained respectively. It is shown from the simulation results that compared with the feedforward-feedback control method, the proposed dynamic sliding mode control strategy based on the established dynamic model is effective to improve the turning control stability of the mobile robot for greenhouse spraying. The experiment results further verify the feasibility of the proposed turning control strategy.

Dynamic Model

Fig. 1 Greenhouse spraying mobile robot

Fig.2 The coordinate system of the mobile robot

D'Alembert Principle

• Establish the dynamic model of the four-wheel mobile robot

formula as (1)、(2)、(3):

$$ma_x = \sum_{i=1}^4 F_{xi} - \frac{1}{2} C_D A_f \rho_a u^2 \quad (1)$$

$$ma_y = \sum_{i=1}^4 F_{yi} \quad (2)$$

$$I_z \dot{\omega}_R = L_f (F_{y1} + F_{y2}) - L_r (F_{y3} + F_{y4}) + \frac{W}{2} (F_{x2} + F_{x4}) - \frac{W}{2} (F_{x1} + F_{x3}) \quad (3)$$

• Establish the dynamic model of four-wheel independent steering formula as (4)、(5):

$$\dot{\beta} = \frac{1}{mu} \left[K_1 \left(\beta + \frac{L_f \omega_R}{u} - \delta_1 \right) + K_2 \left(\beta + \frac{L_r \omega_R}{u} - \delta_2 \right) + K_3 \left(\beta - \frac{L_f \omega_R}{u} - \delta_3 \right) + K_4 \left(\beta - \frac{L_r \omega_R}{u} - \delta_4 \right) \right] - \omega_R \quad (4)$$

$$I_z \dot{\omega}_R = L_f \left[K_1 \left(\beta + \frac{L_f \omega_R}{u} - \delta_1 \right) + K_2 \left(\beta + \frac{L_r \omega_R}{u} - \delta_2 \right) - L_r \left[K_3 \left(\beta - \frac{L_f \omega_R}{u} - \delta_3 \right) + K_4 \left(\beta - \frac{L_r \omega_R}{u} - \delta_4 \right) \right] + \frac{W}{2} (F_{x2} + F_{x4}) - \frac{W}{2} (F_{x1} + F_{x3}) \right] \quad (5)$$

Simulation Results

(a) The control responses of the yaw velocity in a step input

(b) The control responses of the sideslip angle in a step input

Fig. 4 The control responses of the yaw velocity and the sideslip angle in a step input

(a) The control responses of the yaw velocity in a sinusoidal input

(b) The control responses of the sideslip angle in a sinusoidal input

Fig. 5 The control responses of the yaw velocity and the sideslip angle in a sinusoidal input

Design of Controller

The block diagram of the mobile robot control system is shown in Fig.3, and switching surface of the designed sliding mode:

$$s = ce \quad (6)$$

A uniform-speed reaching item is added into the scenario as follow:

$$\frac{d}{dt} s = -\varepsilon \operatorname{sgn}(s) - Ks \quad \varepsilon > 0 \quad (7)$$

According to the exponential reaching law control, have:

$$\frac{d}{dt} s_j = c_j \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\beta} \\ \dot{\omega}_R \end{bmatrix} = -\varepsilon_j \sin n(s_j) - k_j s_j \quad (8)$$

Finally, the control variables can be derived as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \\ \delta_3 \\ \delta_4 \end{bmatrix} = A^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \operatorname{sign}(s_1) + k_1 s_1 - f_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \operatorname{sign}(s_2) + k_2 s_2 - f_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \operatorname{sign}(s_3) + k_3 s_3 - f_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \operatorname{sign}(s_4) + k_4 s_4 - f_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \operatorname{sign}(s_5) + k_5 s_5 - f_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Fig.3 Dynamic sliding mode control block diagram

Experiment Results

Fig. 6 Greenhouse turning tests of mobile robot

Conclusion

- (1) The dynamic model of the mobile robot are established by using the D'Alembert's Principle .
- (2) A dynamic exponential-reaching sliding-mode control strategy is proposed .
- (3) Simulation results that compared with the feedforward-feedback control method show the proposed dynamic sliding mode control strategy based on the established dynamic model is effective to improve the turning control stability of the mobile robot for greenhouse spraying. The experiment results further verify the feasibility of the proposed turning control strategy.

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